

Meeting Visitor Needs at Archaeological Sites: Lessons from Ireland's Wild Atlantic Coast

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Further Reading:

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Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Understanding visitors is essential for effectively managing sustainable tourism at archaeological sites while safeguarding this fragile and invaluable resource. Effective visitor management strategies can ensure visitors have meaningful and enjoyable experiences while exploring the archaeology without causing damage. This study aims to better understand visitor needs at archaeological sites from their perspective. Visitors to six case study sites along the west coast of Ireland were surveyed via an online questionnaire, with the main goal of identifying the key motivations for visiting archaeological sites, the factors influencing visitor satisfaction, and whether visitors are aware of how to avoid damage.

Research Findings

The findings offer valuable insights into tourists' motivations and satisfaction levels at archaeological sites, emphasising their distinct needs as 'archaeotourists'. Insights from Ireland reveal how visitor characteristics influence motivations that extend beyond the site itself to include the surrounding landscape, which affects emotional experiences and enhances satisfaction levels. The findings also identify a clear link between the availability of onsite interpretive information, satisfaction, and conservation. This study underscores the critical role of informed, visitor-centred management in the strategic management of archaeological sites and contributes to discussions on the sustainable management of archaeotourism and the evolving need to conserve archaeological sites.

Policy Implications

Sustainable archaeological site management should prioritise policies that unify visitor experience and conservation, rather than viewing them as conflicting needs to be balanced. As this study demonstrates, visitors value site conservation and are primarily motivated to engage with the landscape and learn about the past. However, those seeking knowledge often leave dissatisfied. The findings reveal significant gaps in interpretation. Policymakers should invest in accessible, high-quality on-site interpretation and guided tours, with guidelines to maintain authenticity and manage visitor expectations. Additionally, strategic support for infrastructure, pathway design, and conservation awareness is essential for reducing footfall impacts and encouraging sustainable visitor behaviour.

Industry Recommendations

Delivering positive visitor experiences requires addressing motivations influenced by season, visitor type, and group composition. Dissatisfaction among those seeking to learn reveals clear gaps in interpretation and guided services. Site managers should prioritise high-quality, accessible information and extended guided tours to improve learning and emotional engagement. Preserving authenticity is vital for increasing perceived value and satisfaction. Practical improvements—paths, signage, access, facilities, conservation—are essential for managing visitors and protecting the landscape. As archaeological tourism grows and sites risk irreversible loss, fostering understanding, sustainable behaviours, and stakeholder collaboration will support long-term protection and adaptive management.

